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MODERN EDUCATIONAL TECHNOLOGIES' SIGNIFICANCE IN THE PROCESS OF
TEACHING CHINESE LANGUAGE

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Abstract. *The introduction of new criteria for teaching foreign languages and the separation of requirements for the caliber of Chinese language acquisition by university students indicate the relevance of this work. The purpose of this paper is to examine cutting-edge, contemporary teaching techniques and technology and use them to instructional activities in order to boost students' enthusiasm for learning Chinese. Moreover, the systematization of the fundamental ideas and procedures for utilizing contemporary educational technology in Chinese classrooms is one of the study's principal conclusions. Teachers of advanced Chinese at schools and universities, as well as educators and others who create educational resources, may find the materials in this page useful. The article covers cutting-edge approaches to teaching foreign languages, the function of information technology, creative ways to teach Chinese, and how to utilize the Internet to teach Chinese. We may also become familiar with contemporary teaching techniques and resources.*

Keywords: *Chinese language, language learning, instructional technologies, communication skills, foreign languages, and creative approaches.*

ЗНАЧЕНИЕ СОВРЕМЕННЫХ ОБРАЗОВАТЕЛЬНЫХ ТЕХНОЛОГИЙ В
ПРОЦЕССЕ ПРЕПОДАВАНИЯ КИТАЙСКОГО ЯЗЫКА

Аннотация. *Введение новых критериев обучения иностранным языкам и разделение требований к уровню владения китайским языком студентами вузов указывают на актуальность данной работы. Цель данной статьи — изучить передовые современные методы и технологии преподавания и использовать их в учебной деятельности, чтобы повысить энтузиазм учащихся в изучении китайского языка. Более того, систематизация фундаментальных идей и процедур использования современных образовательных технологий в китайских классах является одним из основных выводов исследования.*

Преподаватели китайского языка в школах и университетах, а также преподаватели и другие лица, создающие образовательные ресурсы, могут найти полезные материалы на этой странице. В статье рассматриваются передовые подходы к преподаванию иностранных языков, функции информационных технологий, творческие

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способы преподавания китайского языка и способы использования Интернета для обучения китайскому языку. Мы также можем ознакомиться с современными методами преподавания и ресурсами.

Ключевые слова: китайский язык, изучение языка, технологии обучения, коммуникативные навыки, иностранные языки, творческие подходы.

Introduction. In recent decades, there has been a surge of interest in Chinese culture in general and in the Chinese language as an important component of it¹. Every year, more and more students choose to learn Chinese as a foreign language in schools². However, it should be acknowledged that learning Chinese is inevitably challenging, particularly for Russian-speaking pupils when they are just starting out. These are the difficulties associated with mastering hieroglyphic writing (non-alphabetic graphic system, a large number of hieroglyphs, the need to memorize the order of strokes, etc.) and issues related to the phonetic structure of the language, such as the presence of specific sounds that are unusual for Russian phonetics, the presence of tones in syllables, as well as some other nuances due to the peculiarities of the Chinese language³.

In light of this, we believe it is especially important to introduce unconventional teaching strategies and technological tools that will keep students' attention, involve them in language learning, and encourage their active, independent study of foreign language content⁴. Foreign language instructors have long employed a variety of methods and tools to help their pupils become more proficient communicators. The study of foreign languages has recently made active use of relatively new teaching technologies, such as “debates”, case, project, and active learning techniques, among others⁵. They help make classes more exciting and intensive, increase students' interest in the subject, and most importantly, overcome the language barrier. Usually, these technologies allow the simultaneous use of four basic communication skills (speaking, listening, reading and writing).

¹ Moloney R., Hui Ling Xu. Exploring Innovative Pedagogy in the Teaching and Learning of Chinese as a Foreign Language. Spring., 2015. 271 p.

² Alikberova A. Humanitarian communication in the system of Russian-Chinese relations: results of research work // The Turkish Online J. of Design, Art and Communication. TOJDAC Special Ed., 2016. P. 2358–2363.

³ Мордвинова Е.А. Использование технологии дебатов в учебном процессе вуза // Личность, семья и общество : вопросы педагогики и психологии : сб. ст. по материалам II междунар. науч.-практ. конф. №2 : в 2 ч. Новосибирск, 2010. Ч. 1.

⁴ Полат Е.С., Бухаркина М.Ю. Современные педагогические и информационные технологии в системе образования : учеб. пособие для студ. высш. учеб. заведений. М., 2010. 368 с.

⁵ Foyle H.Ch. Interactive Learning in the Higher Education Classroom: Cooperative, Collaborative, and Active Learning Strategies, National Education. Assn, 1995. 237 p

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On the other hand, important prerequisites for bolstering independence include our nation's active involvement in international affairs and the national interests of Uzbekistan's execution of multilateral strategy. The most crucial requirement for this is that Uzbekistan be recognized by the more than 150 nations with which our nation has diplomatic ties. Among them is the People's Republic of China. Uzbekistan and China have had cordial relations for a long time. For many years, the two nations have been enhancing their cultural, political, and economic relations.

Education, of course, demonstrates this kind of relationship. Regarding China-Uzbekistan relations, Uzbek President Sh.M. Mirziyoyev added, "Uzbek-Chinese relations have a long history and date back to the Great Silk Road". The annals of history provide witness to several remarkable instances of the development of sustainable commerce, scientific and humanitarian connections among our peoples, and the enhancement of our customs, traditions, and civilizations⁶.

Science and technology are also rapidly developing in today's rapidly changing world.

Progress in all areas is moving forward. In particular, great changes are taking place in science. Providing students with each subject using new innovative pedagogical technologies is one of the main requirements of modern education.

In teaching a foreign language, it is necessary to use advanced pedagogical technologies, interactive, innovative methods, and communication media. By these requirements, classrooms are equipped with stands and new information and communication technologies. The demand for learning a foreign language is growing day by day. The science of a foreign language is divided into four aspects (reading, writing, speaking, and listening), each of which provides certain concepts and skills.

The efficient application of contemporary information technology to the educational process is known as educational technologies. It also aims to enhance the efficacy and quality of education by incorporating cutting-edge, contemporary technologies into the teaching and learning process. Utilizing these ICTs is very beneficial when learning a foreign language because it offers a number of advantages. Modern technology play a crucial role in language learning and instruction. All facets of learning a foreign language – reading, writing, speaking, and listening – benefit from the use of technology.

Discussion and results. From another point of view, numerous studies confirm that project-based activity is an important component of the productive education system and is an innovative way of organizing educational processes through active methods of action (planning,

⁶ Ш.М. Мирзиёев: «Узбекистан заинтересован в сотрудничестве с Китаем» .Pressservice.uz

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forecasting, analysis, synthesis). The main objectives of using the project method in Chinese language classes:

- to help students acquire the skills and abilities required for various speech activities at the program and standard-determined level;
- to develop listeners' active independence;
- to use Chinese as a medium of intercultural communication in order to engage students in a discussion of cultures;
- to develop communicative ability outside of a language context by making use of the chance to reflect, reason, and concentrate on the statement's content.

The study's findings included the following: schoolchildren and students learning Chinese actively and enthusiastically engage in project work. Students in non-humanitarian specialties, for instance, have the opportunity to apply a creative approach, study in-depth topics that pertain to their professional focus, or study linguistic and cultural issues that they find interesting. All of these opportunities increase students' motivation to study the language in general. There is no restriction on the themes that can be chosen; instead, listeners are encouraged to freely voice their preferences and choose the project's topic based on their personal interests.

Another example would be listening and comprehending; of course, these tasks cannot be completed without a computer, player, or compact discs. One of the most crucial aspects of learning a language is listening. It necessitates that the student focus on the speaker's pronunciation, syntax, vocabulary, and meanings all at once. Students' knowledge of and proficiency with information and communication technologies is a critical component in the integration of these technologies into the classroom. One of the best methods for teaching and studying a foreign language is to use contemporary technologies. During this procedure, which comprises:

- Students can watch and listen to foreign-language films, cartoons, dialogues, and demonstrations on computers;
- students can watch and listen to foreign-language TV shows and radio broadcasts;
- students can use more conventional methods like tape recorders and cassettes.

Students' foreign language learning will be more engaging and successful if they use these resources. With the speed at which the world is changing, it is getting harder to envision our lives without the Internet. One of the best methods for learning and using a foreign language is this one.

Through the Internet, you will be able to speak with people who speak other languages.

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Writing emails can help with written activities. The most crucial issue is the integration of contemporary communication technologies into the educational process and their appropriate, focused application, which encourages students to take an interest in learning a foreign language and improves learning outcomes. This will raise demand and provide opportunities for the usage of cutting-edge educational tools. This will create opportunities for the use of innovative educational technologies and increase demand. Today, several types of innovative educational technologies are available. When they are used widely and in various ways to cover a topic in the classroom, the effectiveness of the lesson is high, and the interest of students in the lesson increases. It is designed to increase the effectiveness of education by introducing and implementing innovations in the educational process. Using a variety of role-playing, and dynamic games in teaching a foreign language will increase interest in both the lesson and learning the language. Working in pairs or small groups, helps students communicate with others. Using graphic organizers in the educational process is one of the most important visits in covering the topic and bringing it to students. You can also use several different graphic organizers to cover the topic. When teaching a foreign language, it is recommended to use graphic organizers to explain new words and grammar rules. They are easy to remember with the help of graphic organizers. It is also very effective to use different tables in the process of teaching a foreign language. Using tables in the learning process, students can follow a certain grammar rule, for example, make sentences using tenses and place new words. In conditions where the need to learn a foreign language is high, effective use of modern information technologies, innovative educational technologies in the educational process makes this process more effective.

Here we have to bring up one of the important advantages of the method is that when preparing a project, students not only have the opportunity to become more familiar with the topic of interest but also often actively use the Chinese segment of the Internet or begin closer communication with native speakers, acquiring extremely important skills in intercultural communication, as well as searching for information in Chinese-language sources and working with it.

Students are encouraged to communicate, think, and create their own ideas thanks to modern tools. Every teacher's primary objective is to pique the student's attention and create situations where he will be forced to talk, listen, and think in a foreign language. They have grown in popularity recently among those who learn foreign languages. This is understandable given their clear advantages and efficacy. Pupils work hard, are motivated, engaged, and communicate.

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Conclusion. To sum up, I'd like to point out that using the project method and debate technology as an alternate teaching approach in Chinese language classes not only helps students expand their vocabulary and improve their phonetic and grammatical skills, but it also fosters a positive attitude toward the subject and the nation where the language is studied, helps students become proficient communicators and public speakers, and makes the learning process more engaging and successful. Thus, There are a number of resources available right now for studying Chinese. In addition, a learner can watch movies, read newspapers and books independently, including those found online, and communicate with native speakers via Skype. It is acceptable to watch both instructional and non-educational movies in class to raise student proficiency in the language, learn new material, and enjoy visual media. Of course, it's important to remember that students shouldn't be exposed to too many new terms, and that classroom movie viewing should be skillfully and methodically organized.

REFERENCES

1. Moloney R., Hui Ling Xu. Exploring Innovative Pedagogy in the Teaching and Learning of Chinese as a Foreign Language. Spring., 2015. 271 p.
2. Alikberova A. Humanitarian communication in the system of Russian-Chinese relations: results of research work // The Turkish Online J. of Design, Art and Communication. TOJDAC Special Ed., 2016. P. 2358–2363.
3. Мордвинова Е.А. Использование технологии дебатов в учебном процессе вуза // Личность, семья и общество : вопросы педагогики и психологии : сб. ст. по материалам II междунар. науч.-практ. конф. №2 : в 2 ч. Новосибирск, 2010. Ч. 1.
4. Полат Е.С., Бухаркина М.Ю. Современные педагогические и информационные технологии в системе образования : учеб. пособие для студ. высш. учеб. заведений. М., 2010. 368 с.
5. Foyle H.Ch. Interactive Learning in the Higher Education Classroom: Cooperative, Collaborative, and Active Learning Strategies, National Education. Assn, 1995. 237 p
6. Ш.М. Мирзиёев: «Узбекистан заинтересован в сотрудничестве с Китаем» .Pressservice.uz
7. Бурцева Э.В. Учебный проект как средство мотивации изучения иностранного языка у студентов неязыкового вуза : автореф. дис. ... канд. пед. наук. Улан-Удэ, 2002. 25 с.
8. Китайско-русский словарь. Пекин: Шанью иньшугуань, 1989.

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9. www.bkrs.info - сайт о китайском языке и Китае, Большой Китайско-Русский Словарь.
10. Сю Цзялу. Толковый словарь современного китайского языка («Xiandai hanyu guifan cidian»). Пекин: Вайюй цзяосюэ юй яньцзю чубаньшэ, 2015.
11. Ergasheva, N. N. (2018). THE EFFECTIVENESS OF USING REALIA IN TEACHING VOCABULARY. Интернаука, (24-3), 45-46.
12. Gulomjonovna, N. N., & Sobirjonovna, M. M. (2019). Peculiarities of using shrines in Fergana Valley for the Purpose of Tourism. International Journal on Integrated Education, 2(6), 1-4.
13. Foyle H.Ch. Interactive Learning in the Higher Education Classroom: Cooperative, Collaborative, and Active Learning Strategies, National Education. Assn, 1995. 237 p.

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